

REPAIR OF AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE USING "HARD" COMPOSITE PATCHES

A. Maier, G. Günther, J. Vilsmeier

Deutsche Aerospace AG

Military Aircraft

P.O. Box 801160

D-8000 München 80

Abstract

With respect to the "on aircraft" repair scenario Deutsche Aerospace (DASA) experience has shown that no satisfactory composite epoxy material is yet available for "vacuum only" - cure cycles to restore design strength of primary aircraft composite structures made of CFRP. This is related to unacceptable high porosity levels in the repair laminates leading to poor mechanical properties and limited inspectability of the repair laminate and bondline.

To overcome this problems DASA developed and improved a repair method for aircraft structure using "Hard" Composite Patches. This method is applicable to curved monolithic and sandwich structures and provides full autoclave repair laminate quality, porous free, high quality bondlines which are fully inspectable by non-destructive testing.

Keywords: Composite Repair, Hard Patch

1. Background

Adhesively bonded repairs are the most common type of repair carried out with composite materials. Bonded repairs can often restore a component to its full design strength and can also restore the original shape and finish to a component which has an aerodynamic surface. The exact details of the repair design and process will largely depend on the materials used and the resources and equipment available. Repairs to hand-lay up components which used room temperature curing resins in the original design are much easier to restore to full strength than components which require heat curing under high pressure in an autoclave.

There are considerably more problems with repairing composites which were originally made using an elevated temperature autoclave cure. Usually it is not possible to use a wet lay-up room temperature curing system in these cases since these systems are unable to give the required hot/wet performance. In this case it would be preferable to use the original prepreg system. However, autoclave curing is unlikely to be available or even possible in a repair situation particularly if removal of the component from the aircraft structure is difficult or impossible. Also a too high curing temperature can cause serious problems for a component which has been in service and may have picked up a significant moisture content. Expansion of the moisture during cure can cause further delamination or porosity in the repair area. For these reasons it is usual to use a lower temperature cure and also to dry the component before repairing [1].

2. Introduction

By using different principles of lay up, staging and precompacting, DASA carried out manufacturing tests by "vacuum only" - curing. The results show that none of the systems, both production prepreg materials (175°C curing systems) and special repair materials available on the market, could meet the general requirement of "vacuum only" - cure. All laminates produced were of bad quality with an unacceptable amount of porosity for application to primary aircraft structure. Porosity however considerably lowers mechanical properties (up to 40%) and decreases the strength and stiffness required for full-flight spectrum capability, furthermore long term effects of porous laminates are not available. More important, porosity also makes inspection of the adhesive bondline beyond the porous CFC-material impossible. This inspection is mandatory to fulfil the basic quality assurance requirements that all structural components in a primary loadpath must be fully inspectable by non-destructive testing [2].

To overcome these problems, DASA developed the "Hard Patch Repair Method" for primary aircraft composite structures.

3. Hard Patch Repair Method

3.1 Repair Approach

Besides the requirement for sufficient static and fatigue strength of the repair itself, it should not change the overall stiffness of the repaired component to avoid additional load concentrations in the structural repair area. "Hard" repair patches are made from unidirectional prepreg tape, cured in an autoclave using standard curing processes. To avoid the effort and time needed for dismantling the damaged structures, the repair on aircraft should be possible by single side access conditions.

3.2 Repair Steps:

The principal flow of work can be divided in ten single steps as shown in Figure 1 to Figure 10.

3.2.1 Step 1: Damage localisation and characterisation by non-destructive inspection (NDI)

The damage is supposed to be a through-the-thickness damage. NDI-testings are performed by using mobile ultrasonic/x-ray equipment.

3.2.2 Step 2: Scarfing of repair area and NDI for soundness of remaining structure

In order to get reproducible results, a circular section is cut out. The cutout is scarfed by routing cutter and sanding paper. The scarf ratio is usually 20:1, but can vary because of laminate thickness and geometric design restrictions. Grinding a scarf needs some workmanship experience. The outline of the individual layers may serve as guidelines as they become visible. After machining non-destructive inspection of remaining structure by mobile ultrasonic should show no further damage.

3.2.3 Step 3: Manufacturing, trimming and bonding of CFRP bottomplate

In order to give a moulding surface to the tool and to get vacuum sealing during the repair a pre-cured GFRP-laminate is fitted to the component. Since it is assumed to have no access to the backside the bottomplate is slipped through the repair hole and bonded to the back face by a room temperature curing adhesive. The advantage of this method is the availability of the whole scarf area for structural load transfer compared to a "fitted-in" bottom plate.

3.2.4 Step 4: Manufacturing of GFRP female tool

The GFRP female tool is manufactured by a glass fabric laminate and a room temperature curing epoxy material which is wet layed up and cured at elevated temperature. The bondline thickness is simulated by release films to match the repair patch loft.

3.2.5 Step 5: Manufacturing of CFRP male tool

The CFRP male tool is manufactured by shaping to the female tool. It is also made by a room temperature curing epoxy material which is wet layed up and cured at elevated temperature. In order to get thermal stability the male tool is post cured at the temperature of the repair material (175°C). This tool is an exact copy of the repair-scarf.

3.2.6 Step 6: Manufacturing of repair patch including NDI

The CFRP male tool is used as tool for manufacturing of the repair patch. The repair patch usually consists of the original prepreg lay-up plus additional cover layers, but can vary with stress/strength analysis requirements. The lay-up and curing is carried out according to the manufacturing process specifications at elevated temperature and with full process pressure in an autoclave. The cured repair patch is inspected by NDI and has to pass quality assurance requirements for normal production components.

3.2.7 Step 7: Staging and embossing of film adhesive

The film adhesive is treated by staging and embossing. This is in order to reduce volatiles and to eliminate low viscosity parts of the adhesive. Simultaneously a continuous groove pattern is embossed to the film adhesive by honeycomb. This creates channels where moisture can be sucked out during cure cycle.

3.2.8 Step 8: Check of bondline by simulation of bonding procedure

The bondline is checked by simulation of the bonding procedure. The film adhesive is separated from structure and repair patch by two release foils. Curing Process will be performed according to Step 9. After cure the film adhesive can be inspected for manufacturing tolerances (visible inspection), thickness, thickness distribution and also by physico-chemical analysis (degree of cure, glass transition temperature).

3.2.9 Step 9: Bonding of repair patch

Bonding of repair patch to structure is carried out by a mobile repair kit. The film adhesive is put on the scarfed cutout, and then the patch is mounted in place. After applying vacuum the adhesive is cured by heat blanket. The cure temperature is reduced from 175°C to 150°C for an extended period because fully assembled parts like wings, horizontal- and vertical stabilizers are not designed to such high thermal loads. Low temperature cure also offers advantages during on-aircraft application at wet structures which were already in service.

3.2.10 Step 10: NDI of repair

The complete repair has to be inspected by ultrasonic and has to pass the quality assurance requirements for production bondlines.

4. Evaluation

4.1. Manufacturing Point of View

The repair technique "Hard Patch Repair" has been tested for different heat curing carbon fibre reinforced composites.

During realization of the repair method by different materials no significant changes in repair-processing and -manufacturing tasks were necessary whereas material specific manufacturing properties (e.g. bleeding) have to be taken into consideration. The efforts both in time and labor are higher compared to repairs by wet lay up and requires also higher skill of personnel.

4.2. Engineering Point of View

Feasibility studies prove that this repair method can be transformed to the different production materials and requires no special repair materials. This saves additional material qualification efforts. The results gathered are within specification and quality assurance requirements. Parent material with original cure cycle can be used as repair material with identical properties and without porosity in the repair patch. No qualification of repair materials is necessary. The bondline is inspectable using standard production NDI techniques. Adhesive treatment by staging and embossing minimizes porosity in bondline.

Verification of repair bonding by using "verifilm-technique" (see Step 7 above) showed that the cured film adhesive has a constant thickness by visible inspection. The thickness measurements are within a narrow range. Physico-chemical analysis by Differential-Scanning-Calorimetry showed a full cure of the adhesive and a glass transition temperature which is well above service temperature of fighter aircraft.

A destructive inspection by microsection of the repaired area showed little voids in the bondline not detectable by mobile ultrasonic equipment. The repair patch is void free and without porosity. The thickness measurements of bondline is corresponding well to the thickness measurements of the cured film adhesive produced by "verifilm-technique". The accuracy of the repair is within narrow tolerances. The adherents are well joined by the adhesive and the interfaces indicate no disbonding.

Test results obtained from tensile coupon specimens have shown excellent mechanical properties of the repair.

5. Summary

The repair method using "Hard" composite patches described above restores full structural integrity to damaged composite aircraft structures exceeding design strength levels. It has to be properly designed and processed and takes relatively high efforts in time and labor, but reduces time for aircraft and parts disassembly.

Future work is dedicated to standardize and simplify the repair procedure, as well as to perform qualification steps for "on aircraft" applications.

6. References

- [1] Corbet, D.C., *Repair of composites-an overview*, Bonding and Repair of Composites, 14. July 1989 Metropole Hotel, National Exhibition Centre, Birmingham, UK
- [2] Vilsmeier, J.W., *Composite Repair of Aircraft Structures*, Composite Structure Repair, Addendum to AGARD Report No. 716

Step 1:
Damage localisation and
characterisation by NDI

Figure 1

Step 2:
Scarifying of repair area and NDI for
soundness of remaining structure

Figure 2

Step 3:
Manufacturing, trimming and
bonding of CFRP bottomplate

Figure 3

Step 4:
Manufacturing of
GFRP female tool

Figure 4

Step 5:
Manufacturing of
CFRP male tool

Figure 5

Step 6:
Manufacturing of repair patch
including NDI

Figure 6

Step 7:
Staging and embossing
of film adhesive

Figure 7

Step 8:
Check of bondline by
simulation of bonding procedure

Figure 8

Step 9:
Bonding of
repair patch

Figure 9

Step 10:
NDI of Repair

Figure 10